

TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION: PERCEPTIONS OF ENGLISH-MAJORED STUDENTS AT HUPI

Nguyen Thi Xuyen

Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry

Email: xuyenhbt.nguyen@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Although there have been a considerable number of studies on the perspectives of teachers' on the teaching and learning of English pronunciation in Vietnam, learner's perceptions on the same issue seem to be ignored. This study is carried out with the aim of investigating learner's perceptions on the acquisition and instruction of English pronunciation at HUPI so that the current situation of teaching and learning English pronunciation at Faculty of Foreign Languages at HUPI will be revealed. In order to get the data for analysis, a questionnaire is used. The findings show the common goals, methods of learning and difficulties in learning the pronunciation of English-majored students as well as their perspectives on the teaching of English pronunciation at HUPI. Based on the findings, some possible solutions are suggested to enhance the situation.

Key words: English pronunciation, English majors, perceptions, acquisition, instruction.

1 INTRODUCTION

Undeniably, English has become the language of international communication and a good command of English is considered a prerequisite to get a good job in many countries worldwide, including Vietnam. It is widely accepted that good pronunciation enhances both the intelligibility and the effectiveness of our speech. Watkins (2008) states that poor pronunciation can impede communication quickly because a speaker who perceives that their pronunciation is not proficient enough may lose their confidence and then performs worse in other aspects of speaking such as maintaining fluency. Celce-Murcia et al. (2012) believes that there is a "threshold level" of pronunciation for those who are not native English speakers to pass; otherwise, they will have problems with their oral communication no matter how excellent and extensive their grammar and vocabulary might be.

In Vietnam, the National Foreign Languages 2020 project has driven more and more attention to English pronunciation, and made it no longer a neglected aspect (Dao, 2018) because Vietnamese learners and teachers started to recognize its important role in communicating. However, English pronunciation acquisition is not an easy task for English learners in general and for Vietnamese students in particular. According to Cunningham (2009), the English spoken by most of learners in Vietnam is not intelligible enough for foreigners, especially for those from English-speaking countries.

In order to shed light on what makes the acquisition of English pronunciation so challenging for Vietnamese learners, a significant number of research have been carried out with a focus on the phonological differences between English and Vietnamese. Nguyen (2007) has identified nine

challenges that Vietnamese learners usually face when pronouncing English final consonants. According to Tuan (2011), Vietnamese students have most troubles pronouncing the English fricatives /ʃ/ and /ʒ/ and the affricatives /tʃ/ and /dʒ/. Yen (2016) conducted a research into the learning and teaching of English pronunciation in Vietnam, and she concluded that beside phonological matters, there are non-phonological factors affecting the English pronunciation acquisition and instruction of Vietnamese learners. She mentioned learning and teaching methods, exposure time to English, the confusion in choosing the English pronunciation models to follow and the necessary environment to apply what they have learnt (Yen, 2016).

English Pronunciation is a compulsory course in the curriculum for English majors at Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry (HUPI). All students have already learnt English pronunciation; however, many of them still have problems pronouncing English.

Recognizing the importance of English pronunciation teaching and learning in communicating, the current study is conducted in the hope to evaluate the current practice of pronunciation learning and teaching at HUPI, especially, English-majored students' perceptions towards English pronunciation instruction and acquisition will be investigated. The study uses the claim made by Yen (2016) that "there are indeed non-phonological factors" that affect the learning and teaching of English pronunciation. More particularly, the study is taken to answer the following research questions:

1. What do English-majored students at HUPI want to achieve in learning English pronunciation?
2. What are the perceptions of English-majored students at HUPI towards the learning of English pronunciation?
3. What are the perceptions of English-majored students at HUPI towards the teaching of English pronunciation?

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Learning goals

Different learners want to learn English for different reasons. However, when the goals of English acquisition and instruction are taken into account, there are two widely accepted opposing principles: the nativeness or the intelligibility (Levis, 2005). While the former principle holds that learners should learn to pronounce like native speakers, the later proposes that EFL learners should aim to achieve a "functional comprehensible speech" and that "learners with foreign accents are able to achieve fluency as long as their accents do not impede the intelligibility of their speech" (Levis, 2005).

Recently the emergence of English as an international language has raised the need to reconsider the goals for English pronunciation learning and teaching and the intelligibility principle has received more attention from English teachers and researchers. However, several studies conducted in Vietnam have found out that native-like accents such as American English or British English are still considered the major goals in learning English pronunciation by the vast majority of learners (Yen, 2016; Ngan (2018)). In addition, according to Dao (2018) and Yen (2016), most of Vietnamese learners prefer American English to British English.

The present study aims to identify what English majors at HUPI want to achieve in learning English pronunciation in order to help teachers adopt the appropriate teaching methods.

2.2 English pronunciation learning difficulties

Gilakjani (2012) states that foreign language learners undeniably encounter difficulties in pronouncing even after a long time of learning the language. Several researchers in Vietnam have attempted to find out the difficulties that English language learners in Vietnam met when learning English pronunciation and most of them focus on phonological aspects. For example, Tam (2005) discovered that there are three errors that Vietnamese learners usually made when pronouncing English sounds: sound omission (medial and final sounds), sound confusion and sound redundancy (Tam, 2005). Similarly, Nguyen (1998) also investigated learners' omission of final consonant sounds and distinction of long and short vowels in order to validate the claim that English sounds made by Vietnamese learners are too short.

Few researches have also been carried out by Vietnamese teachers to clarify learner's difficulties in learning English pronunciation from the learners' point of view. According to Yen (2016), English stress/rhythm/intonation is the most problematic aspect when learning English pronunciation, followed by being heavily affected by mother tongue. Her study also revealed that the difficulties in learning English pronunciation mainly emerge from their learning methods as well as lack of real environment to use English. Ngan (2018) found out that students did not have sufficient time to practice English pronunciation during in-class work periods, which are the main factors that hamper learner's pronunciation skills.

This study attempts to reveal the English majors' difficulties in learning pronunciation as well as their attitude towards the acquisition of pronunciation so that English teachers will be able to plan for more effective learning.

2.3 English pronunciation instruction in classrooms

According to Gilakjani and Ahmadi (2011), pronunciation is "one of the least favorable topics for teachers to address in the classroom". Research has found out several common problems encountered by teachers when teaching pronunciation such as lack of background knowledge, shortage of confidence to assess questionable pronunciation practices in their teaching materials (Thomson, 2012). In addition, lack of ability to teach pronunciation and the insufficient teacher training programs are also cited by several researchers as the significant problems language teachers encounter when teaching pronunciation (Foote, Holtby & Derwing, 2012, cited in Yen (2016)).

In Vietnam, just a few studies have been conducted to investigate the difficulties in teaching English pronunciation. Yen (2016) who studied the learner's beliefs about the problems that their teachers have when teaching pronunciation, revealed that teaching behavior seems to be the most problematic to Vietnamese teachers, followed by lack of confidence and poor English proficiency.

3 METHODOLOGY

The participants of this study are 50 freshmen studying in Faculty of Foreign Languages at HUFU. Of 50 students, 36 are female and 14 are male, aged largely from 18 to 20. All of the participants have been studying English pronunciation at HUFU for five weeks. According to the curriculum for English majors at HUFU, pronunciation course lasts 15 weeks with two-period lesson each week. Vietnamese teachers and foreign teachers cooperate in teaching English pronunciation to English majors. The local teachers are responsible for two thirds of the class time and the rest will be for the foreign teachers.

In the light of the nature of the research questions, a questionnaire is used to examine the English-major freshmen’s perceptions towards the acquisition and instruction of English pronunciation at HUFU. The 20-item questionnaire is developed after the researcher reviewed the instruments used in previous studies such as Elliot (1995), Yen (2016) and Ngan (2018). Some items are modified and others are added to make the questionnaire suitable and relevant to English-major students at HUFU. The questionnaires are distributed to the respondents when they have learned English pronunciation at HUFU for five weeks.

The questionnaire includes five sections: participant’s background information, the importance and the main goals of English pronunciation acquisition, English pronunciation acquisition, English pronunciation instruction and attitudes towards English pronunciation acquisition. In order to obtain all this information, a variety of question types are applied including multiple-choice questions, yes-no questions, direct questions and open-ended questions. Thanks to those types of questions, both quantitative and qualitative data can be achieved in this study.

In addition, this study also aims to reveal the attitude of English-major freshmen towards English pronunciation; hence, the Pronunciation Attitude Inventory (PAI) is adopted. The PAI used in this study is adopted from Yen (2016) with nine statements. Each statement is followed by the numbers from one to five and the participants have to choose among 1=strongly disagree, 2=somewhat disagree, 3=neither agree nor disagree, 4=somewhat agree, 5=strongly agree. After that, the total scores of each student are calculated with the maximum score of 45. The idea of PAI is that the higher the score is, the more positive attitude the participant has towards English pronunciation.

Criteria for judging the attitude towards pronunciation of English majors at HUFU

	Very negative	Negative	Neutral	Positive	Very positive
Total scores (45)	1-18	18 – 22.5	22.5	22.5 - 36	36-45
Mean	1.0-2.0	2.1 – 2.5	2.6 – 3.0	3.1 – 4.0	4.0 -5.0

The quantitative data collected via questionnaire is calculated using the Analysis Tool pack of Excel and only descriptive statistical analyses are performed.

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Findings

4.1.1 Students’ background information

Some profile questions are asked in the questionnaire in order to have a better understanding of English majors background. The results show that a majority of participants (82%) have learnt English for more than six years. It is also worth noting that 88% of participants reveal that up to time of being surveyed they rarely or sometimes use English in real contexts in spite of learning English for a long time.

Figure 1: Learners' years of learning English

Figure 2: Frequency of using English

In addition, the survey questions the students about what aspects of English they focus on when learning English and there is more than one aspect that is labelled. As illustrated in Figure 3, speaking, vocabulary and listening are indicated by most learners with proportions of 80%, 72% and 68% respectively. The results show grammatical rules have received less attention from English majors at HUFU than other factors such as vocabulary or listening skills. This finding seems to be surprising because grammar used to be allocated a significant amount of time in the English class curriculum in Vietnam.

Figure 3: Focus of English acquisition

The participants are also asked to evaluate their own proficiency level of English pronunciation. The results reveal that almost all the participants (94%) identify themselves at B1 or lower level. It is also noteworthy that more than half of the students seem to lack self-confidence when self-considering their pronunciation proficiency only at A1 level.

Figure 4: Students' self-report of English pronunciation proficiency

4.1.2 Students’ perceptions towards the importance of English pronunciation and their main goal in English pronunciation

The survey asks the students to express their perceptions towards the role of English pronunciation in communication. As illustrated in the Table 1, 76% of the participants consider pronunciation as the most important factor to communicate with people from other cultures and almost all of them (94%) state that poor pronunciation can be a barrier in communication. According to those students, mispronunciation not only makes the speaker less self-confident but also causes misunderstanding between the speaker and the listener, which hinders the conversation flow.

Table 1: Students’ perception towards the role of English pronunciation

Issues	Responses	Number of students’ responses	Percentages of students’ responses
What is the key to success when communicating with foreigners?	Pronunciation	38	76%
	Grammar	2	6%
	Culture	1	2%
	Fluency	8	16%
Is pronunciation a barrier to communicate with foreigners?	Yes	47	94%
	No	3	6%

When being asked which models of English pronunciation they prefer to learn, 52% of the students choose American English. The proportions of students who choose British English and other English varieties are quite low, at 28% and 20% respectively. The most common reason that they cite for their preference of American English is its popularities and easiness to acquire. What they mean is that the American accent is more widely-used in communication, textbooks and movies. Some students state that they prefer American English because it sounds more beautiful and softer.

For those who choose varieties of English other than American or British English, they believe in future it is more likely that they will work with people from non-native English speaking countries such as the Philippines, Singapore, or India than those from Great Britain or the USA.

4.1.3 Students’ perceptions towards the learning of English pronunciation at HUF1

The survey asks students to express their opinions on the English pronunciation acquisition at HUF1. The data indicates that all of the participants recognize the crucial role of English pronunciation acquisition, 72% of whom state that it is very important to study English pronunciation. The most common reason cited by the participants is that learning pronunciation helps improve their speaking proficiency as well as their confidence when communicating with foreigners. Therefore, 100% students answer that apart from learning pronunciation with teachers two 45-minute lessons every week, they also practice pronunciation outside the class time. Interestingly, 76% of students practice English pronunciation on their own via pronunciation apps on their mobile phone or by watching videos on YouTube whereas only 30% and 10% of the participants learn with friends or with foreigners respectively.

The results of the survey also reveal the difficulties of English-majored freshmen in English pronunciation acquisition. As illustrated in Figure 5, the little correspondence between the sounds and the written forms of English words causes problems for 64% of the respondents, making it the most challenging aspect of English pronunciation learning. The difficulties caused by perceiving and producing problematic sounds and English stress/rhythm/intonation are reported by 58% and 50% of the freshmen respectively. A significant percentage of respondents (46%) admit that their mother tongue influences their English so heavily that their English sounds like Vietnamese.

Figure 5: Difficulties in learning English pronunciation

When being questioned which factors hinder their pronunciation proficiency, a majority of respondents (70%) complain that they do not have enough chances to use English to communicate in real-life contexts. In addition, 64% of the participants admit that their learning methods are not appropriate, which also causes a lot of difficulties for them in English pronunciation acquisition. It is also noteworthy that a significant percentage of respondents blame teacher’s ineffective teaching methods for hampering their learning of pronunciation, whereas, insufficient time for learning and practicing pronunciation is cited by only a small proportion of participants (10%).

Figure 6: Reasons for difficulties in learning English pronunciation

4.1.4 Students' perceptions towards the teaching of English pronunciation at HUFU

The survey also asks students to evaluate the English pronunciation teaching at HUFU. Firstly, the respondents have to choose between local and foreign teachers as their preferred pronunciation instructor. It is not surprising that 75% of the participants desire to learn English pronunciation from foreign teachers while only 25% choose to learn with Vietnamese teachers. Similarly, when being asked who can best teach them English pronunciation, 70% of the participants choose teachers who are native English speakers from Great Britain, the USA or Australia while Vietnamese teachers with overseas training are the preferred choices of only 26% of the participants

Students are also questioned to explain what makes them choose either local or foreign teachers. The results reveal that the most important factors that affect the students' choice of either local or foreign teachers are the friendly personality (34 out of 50), the ability to understand and speak English fluently (32), the ability to make lessons interesting (28) and the enthusiastic personality (27). Teaching experience, qualification and culture understanding are scored a bit lower by 23, 20 and 18 students respectively.

In addition, it is also worth noting that the reasons that the students mention for their choice of either local or foreign teachers are the same while the value of each reason is quite different between the two types of teachers. As illustrated in Figure 7, local teachers are preferred mainly due to their ability to understand the students' culture (90%), their friendly personality (85%) and their enthusiasm (70%), while the most common reasons for the foreign teachers to be preferred are their ability to understand/speak English fluently, interesting classes and their friendly personality (80%, 65% and 63% respectively).

Figure 7: Factors affecting students' choice of local or foreign teachers

The survey also asks the students to express their views on the challenges that Vietnamese teachers and teachers from other countries may encounter when teaching English pronunciation for English majors at HUFU. The results show that while a majority of participants (74%) state that Vietnamese teachers may encounter difficulties because of their teaching behaviors, 90% of them mention that foreign teachers may have difficulties explaining theoretical things to students because of their inability to know Vietnamese.

Table 2: Students’ perceptions of difficulties in teaching pronunciation of local and foreign teachers

Teachers	Difficulties in teaching Pronunciation	Percentages
Local teachers	Not confident	36%
	Poor English proficiency	5%
	Teaching behavior	74%
	Do not understand student’s culture	32%
Foreign teacher	Lack of pedagogy training	4%
	Difficult to explain theoretical things	90%

In order to help students learn pronunciation better, six potential ways are recommended for teachers to do, and the students are asked to choose all the suggestions that are suitable with them. According to the Figure 8, 68% of students would like teachers to correct their pronunciation mistakes immediately and more frequently in class as well as to create a friendly learning environment so that the students can feel more confident to speak English. In addition, when being asked to clarify what their teachers should do to enhance the quality of their English pronunciation instruction, many participants state that teachers should use multi-media materials such as films, songs, or videos. In addition, more than half of the respondents indicate that teachers should understand the needs as well as the difficulties in learning English pronunciation of their students in order to find out appropriate methods to help them overcome. A significant proportion of students (34%) also suggest that teachers should continuously study to improve their English pronunciation knowledge, especially by taking training courses overseas so that they can be more competent and confident in teaching English pronunciation.

Figure 8: Students’ perceptions of ways teachers can do to help learners learn EP

4.1.5 Students’ attitude toward English pronunciation

By analyzing the results of PAI, the attitudes of English majors at HUFU towards English pronunciation are revealed. As illustrated in Table 3, the average total score of all respondents is

36.5 with Mean = 4 and Std. Dev = 1.14, which means that all of the students have positive and very positive attitudes towards learning English pronunciation.

Table 3: PAI overall score

PAI overall score	Number of learners	%
27	1	2%
28	1	2%
30	1	2%
31	2	4%
32	2	4%
33	8	16%
34	2	4%
35	5	10%
36	2	4%
37	5	10%
38	5	10%
39	3	6%
40	3	6%
41	3	6%
42	2	4%
43	4	8%
44	1	2%
Average: 36.5	N = 50	100%

4.2 Discussion

Firstly, the findings of this study clearly show that English majors at HUFU have very positive attitude to English pronunciation. Most of them well recognize the importance of pronunciation in communicating with foreigners. In addition, a majority of English majors at HUFU still aim at achieving American English or British English accent while other varieties of English seem not to be preferred by many students. It is noteworthy, however, that in the context of Vietnam where English is still considered and mostly used as a foreign language, it is more likely that learners will communicate with people from non-native English speaking countries such as China, the Philippines, Japan or Korea, and therefore, intelligible pronunciation should be more realistic and achievable for English learners. However, while English majors still consider native-like accents as a proof of language competence, this goal will become a “burden” for both the teachers and learners (Dao, 2018). Therefore, right at the beginning of the course, teachers should base on the learning conditions as well as the potential context where English will be used to set an achievable and realistic goal. Moreover, students need to be persuaded to accept this goal so that the teachers can adopt the teaching methods as well as the materials which are suitable for their students, and the learners will have appropriate learning methods.

Secondly, findings reveal that English majors at HUFU encounter different problems when learning English. Most of these difficulties arise from the difference in the phonological systems of English and Vietnamese languages such as the correspondence between the sounds and the written forms of English words, the problematic sounds (/ð/, /ʒ/) as well as stress/rhythm or intonation. It is also clear from the results of this study that the main reasons that cause difficulties in mastering English

pronunciation are the lack of environment for them to use English in real communication situations, the learners' inappropriate learning methods and the ineffective teaching practices of the teachers. In order to improve this situation, it is suggested that the administrators should create an English-speaking environment for students to apply what they learn, and students should be introduced the best methods to acquire English pronunciation both in-class periods and out-class ones.

Finally, the findings of the current study also reveal that between local teachers and foreign teachers, students prefer to be taught by native-English speaking teachers mainly due to the fact that the native teachers can understand and speak English more fluently than the Vietnamese teachers. Students also complain the teaching behaviors of their teachers and would like their teachers to change in order to help them learn English pronunciation better. From the findings, it is suggested that teachers should vary their teaching techniques and make their classrooms a friendlier and more exciting learning environment so that learners can be more interested in learning as well as become more self-confident to speak English. In addition, it will be better if teachers give more feedback on students' pronunciation; allow more time for them to practice pronunciation as well as integrate pronunciation into other English courses.

5 CONCLUSION

This study has attempted to investigate the perceptions of English majors at HUFU towards the actual situation of learning and teaching English pronunciation at HUFU, using the claim made by Yen (2016) that there are non-phonological factors affecting the English pronunciation acquisition and instruction.

The results of the study show the main aim of learning English pronunciation of English majors at HUFU, the difficulties they encounter when learning pronunciation and the situation of teaching pronunciation at HUFU.

Regarding the main goal of English pronunciation acquisition, the current study has pointed out that most learners aim to achieve native-like accent while intelligible seems to be achievable and useful for them. About the learners' perception towards the acquisition and instruction of English pronunciation at HUFU, a majority of students recognize the role of pronunciation in communication and they indeed encounter difficulties in pronunciation acquisition largely due to their lack of real English environment and their learning methods. The students also express their preference of native teachers and suggest several ways for teachers to improve their teaching behaviors.

From the findings, some suggestions are also made in this study for teachers and administrators to enhance the English pronunciation teaching and learning situation at HUFU.

This study still has some limitations that open up potential topics for future research. Firstly, the present study investigates the perceptions of learners only while teachers and administrators of the faculty are not questioned, which leads to one-way views on the acquisition and instruction of English pronunciation at HUFU. In addition, using only questionnaires to collect data limits the opportunities for the respondents to clarify their opinions. Therefore, in the future research, it would be better if both teachers, learners and administrators' views are surveyed and interviewed to provide more valuable and reliable information for the research.

REFERENCES

- [1] Celce-Murcia, M., Brinton, D. & Goodwin, J. (2012). *Teaching pronunciation: A course book and reference guide* (2nd edition). New York: Cambridge University Press.
- [2] Cunningham, U.(2009). Models and Targets for the Pronunciation of English in Vietnam and Sweden. *Research in Language*, 7, 113-128.
- [3] Dao, D (2018). Learners' perspectives on English pronunciation teaching and learning: a preliminary study in the Vietnamese context. *Proceedings of the 9th Pronunciation in Second Language Learning and Teaching conference*, pp. 86-99. Retrieved from <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/330114452>.
- [4] Elliot, A.R. (1995). Foreign language phonology: Field independence, attitude, and the success of formal instruction in Spanish pronunciation. *The Modern Language Journal*, 79(4), 530-542.
- [5] Gilakjani, A.P. (2012). The significance of pronunciation in English language teaching. *English language teaching*, 5(4), 96.
- [6] Gilakjani, A.P., & Ahmadi, M. (2011). Why is pronunciation so difficult to learn? *English Language Teaching*, 4(3), 74.
- [7] Levis, J.M. (2005). Changing contexts and shifting paradigms in pronunciation teaching. *Tesol Quarterly*, 39(3), 369-377.
- [8] Ngan, T.N.T (2018). The extent to which the Vietnamese teachers' perspectives on English pronunciation education correlate with those of the Vietnamese learners'. Retrieved from <http://theses.ubn.ru.nl>.
- [9] Nguyen, T.T.T. (2007). Difficulties for Vietnamese when pronouncing English: Final consonants.
- [10] Nguyen, T.(2017). Vietnam's National Foreign Language 2020 Project after 9 years: A difficult Stage. Paper presented in the Asian conference on Education & International Development 2017, pp. 1-22.
- [11] Tam, H.C. (2005). Common pronunciation problems of Vietnamese learners of English. *Journal of Science Foreign Language*. Retrieved from <http://news.vnu.edu.vn>
- [12] Thomson, R.I. (2012). ESL teacher's beliefs and practices in pronunciation teaching: confidently right or confidently wrong. In *Proceedings of the 4th Pronunciation in Second Language Learning and Teaching Conference*. (pp. 224-233)
- [13] Tuan, L.T. (2011). Vietnamese EFL learners' Difficulties with English consonants. *Studies in Literature and Language*, 3(2), 56-67.
- [14] Watkins, P. (2008). *Learning to Teach English*. Surrey: Delta Publishing.
- [15] Yen, V.H. (2016). Exploring English pronunciation teaching in Vietnam: Time for a new approach? Retrieved from <http://www.researchonline.mq.edu.au>